

Incentivizing Open Data Within African Academia

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Executive Summary

“The nature of science is changing from a closed system to an open and sharing one. It affects virtually all components of doing science and research, and shifts in particular the focus from ‘publishing as fast as possible’ to ‘sharing knowledge as early as possible’” (Hodson et al., 2018, p. 1).

Open Science is defined as research and development (R&D) that is “collaborative, transparent and reproducible and whose outputs are publicly available” (European Commission, 2018, p. 4). It represents a new approach to R&D that encourages cooperation and sharing through the use of digital technologies and new collaborative tools.

The idea captures a systemic change to the way science and research have been carried out for the last fifty years: shifting from the standard practices of publishing research results in scientific publications towards sharing and using all available knowledge at an earlier stage in the research process (European Commission, 2016, p. 33). Open Science is more than open access to publications or data; it includes many aspects and stages of research processes. It is commonly recognized that the Open Science movement rests on three key pillars: open access to scientific information, open data and open engagement with society (including firms) (Hodson et al., 2018, p. 2).

This report focuses primarily on Open Data, as a sub-set of Open Science activities. Open Data promote the idea of research data being shared for scrutiny and re-analysis without unnecessary barriers. Open Data activities promote the notion that “making data accessible is not enough” (International Council for Science et al., 2015, p. 4). They advocate for “intelligent openness” (Royal Society, 2012, p. 15) by which data are “discoverable, accessible, intelligible, assessable, and usable (International Council for Science et al., 2015, p. 4).

Sharing data is both a practical challenge and a change of traditional attitudes to data ownership. The Open Data movement combines the “use of new digital tools, a specific set of values, and/or practices of collaboration and sharing” (Leonelli, 2017, p. 4). Activities thus range from education and the promotion of cultures of sharing, to research data management and standard setting. These activities include not only researchers, but also scientific publishers, research institutions, national governments and funders.

Two key challenges face the current Open Data movement. The first is the understanding that there can be no “one size fits all” when it comes to research data management and “intelligent openness”. Responsible data practices may vary considerably based on the discipline, types of data and community requirements. Second, there remain considerable technical and social challenges to sharing data. These range from infrastructural challenges to scientists’ concerns about losing control of their data and being “scooped”. For researchers in Africa, these challenges are often compounded by resource-constrained research settings, historical academic legacies and a paucity of established data sharing cultures *in situ*.

This framework considers how cultures of Open Data can be fostered within African academia. The outline is schematically represented in the figure below (1). The framework proposes an approach that capitalizes on existing inputs, such as Open Science resources, the goodwill generated by the AOSP, and communities of expertise within African research institutions and networks. It considers how these positive inputs can be used to address some of the constraints that would undermine Open Data activities on the continent.

In proposing areas of activity, the framework considers two distinct, but complimentary areas. It considers how recognition of the value of Open Data can be fostered amongst research stakeholders. It also considers how this cultural change can be supported by ameliorating key physical, regulatory and social barriers to Open Data practices. Key areas of recommendation include the re-evaluation of promotion criteria to reward Open Science activities, improved training in research data management and Open Data practices, and the recognition of data collections as an asset to attract international attention.

These different areas of activity do not only relate to researchers, but also to funders, publishers, institutions, national governments and NRENS. This demonstrates the need for widespread commitment to supporting Open Data practices if they are to become the norm for African research.

Figure 1: Schematic overview of incentivization framework

The efficacy of efforts to incentivize Open Data activities must be measured by a range of different outputs. The activities proposed by the framework cover a range of different areas, from changing research cultures, educational capacity building, regulatory and evaluation criteria development and national buy-in. The outputs by which these different activities can be measured are similarly varied and include scrutinizing the rate of data depositions from African researchers, conducting regular regulatory reviews and collating changes in metrics for academic evaluation.

Some of the activities proposed require financial and human-resource investment, while others can be conducted with relatively little resource commitment. The framework thus proposes that activities to incentivise Open Data be viewed in terms of short, medium and long-term timeframes. This will avoid overburdening current research systems, while also safeguarding against disappointment and fatigue. Ultimately, however, the framework proposes that effectively incentivizing Open Data amongst research stakeholders will make data sharing the default norm in African research and a mark of quality that defines research outputs from the continent.

Open Science and Open Data: a Brief Introduction

Open Science

The nature of research is changing rapidly. In recent years, the focus has shifted from the standard practices of publishing research results in scientific publications towards sharing and using all available knowledge at an earlier stage in the research process (European Commission, 2015, p. 33). This has led to a change in priorities, from “‘publishing as fast as possible’ to ‘sharing knowledge as early as possible’” (Hodson *et al.*, 2018, p. 1), and the evolution of the Open Science movement.

The commitment to openness is by no means a new concept in academic research. Indeed, public scrutiny, transparency and the reproducibility of results have formed the bedrock of research since the scientific revolution (Merton, 1942; Popper, 1992). Nonetheless, it is only in recent decades that the Open Science movement has come to be formally recognized as a commitment towards developing “transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed through collaborative networks” (Vicente-Saez and Martinez-Fuentes, 2018, p. 428).

The value of openness in research is well-recognized. In the recent South Africa-European Union Open Science Dialogue Report, key benefits were identified to:

- (i) science itself: it improves efficiency and the verifiability of science, it brings transparency, and it allows inter-disciplinarity
- (ii) the economy: with wider access to, and increased re-use of scientific information by all, and in particular, by industry and innovative companies
- (iii) society: it brings broader, faster, transparent and equal access for citizens, and contributes to increased societal impact of science and research (Hodson *et al.*, 2018, p. 1)

FOSTER defines Open Science as “the practice of science in such a way that others can collaborate and contribute, where research data, lab notes and other research processes are freely available, under terms that enable reuse, redistribution and reproduction of the research

and its underlying data and methods”.¹ Open Science is best understood as an umbrella concept constituted of multiple movements that work to remove the barriers for sharing any kind of output, resources, methods or tools, at any stage of the research process. These movements include open access to publications, open research data, open source software, open collaboration, open peer review, open notebooks, open educational resources, open monographs, citizen science, and open hardware.² All of these areas are united by a commitment to ensuring that research is “collaborative, transparent and reproducible and whose outputs are publicly available” (European Commission, 2018, p. 4).

All facets of the Open Science movement are based on the “three pillars of Open Science”. These are “open access to scientific information, open data and open engagement with society (including firms)” (Hodson *et al.*, 2018, p. 2). In understanding the variety of activities within each pillar, it is helpful to think of Open Science as both an ideological commitment to just resource distribution as well as the practical use of evolving digital tools, specific definitions of Open Science may vary (Levin *et al.*, 2016). Open Science activities can therefore involve the developing new digital tools, identifying specific values, and/or establishing practices of collaboration and sharing (Leonelli, 2017, p. 4). Indeed, embracing all aspects of Open Science is helpful for conceptualising how openness can be integrated into different aspects of modern research. As highlighted by Leonelli (2016), debates about Open Science offer important opportunities to consider what does/should count as high-quality research, what research goals are worthwhile pursuing, how research findings should be evaluated and disseminated, and what relationship should exist between science and society.

It is important to recognize how commitments to Open Science represent a shift in current practices of research, publishing and evaluation, and necessarily affect all stages of the research process (Leonelli, 2017). Nonetheless, openness *per se* is not sufficient in itself. Instead, the Open Science movement advocates for “intelligent openness” (Boulton *et al.*, 2012, p. 14) that ensures that all aspects of the research lifecycle are governed by a commitment to openness. These different areas are represented in figure 2 below.

¹ <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/foster-taxonomy/open-science-definition>

² <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/content/what-open-science-introduction>

Figure 2: Open Science and the research lifecycle

Source: <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/content/what-open-science-introduction>

Figure 2 also draws attention to the need for Open Science activities to be supported by policy mandates and appropriate incentive, monitoring and reward systems (Hodson *et al.*, 2018, p. 2). Moreover, while the Open Science movement is united globally by commitments to egalitarianism, the manner in which Open Science activities are implemented within specific disciplines or national science systems can (and should) vary according to differences in data, research contexts and legal frameworks. Ensuring effective Open Science practices requires the commitment of multiple stakeholders, including researchers, research institutions, national governments, National Research and Education Networks (NRENs), funders and the global research community.

Open Science represents an exciting, and continually evolving landscape that is defining future research practices, cultures and governance. Support for Open Science practices is growing rapidly in the African research community, and it is recognized that African research stands to benefit from the Open Science movement. In particular, enhancing practices of openness in African research will foster connections between researchers and the public, improve the

competitiveness of research by speeding up knowledge transfers, and enhance local and global collaborations (Hodson *et al.*, 2018, p. 2).

As outlined in the African Open Science Platform (AOSP) vision document (v02), activities such as the AOSP “will facilitate data-intensive, solutions-oriented research, bringing scientists and non-scientists together as knowledge partners in open networks of collaborative learning and problem solving. In this way the Platform will drive the creation of actionable knowledge and strengthen the credibility, practical relevance and socio-political legitimacy of science in and for Africa” (African Open Science Platform, 2018, p. 7). As practices of openness are increasingly becoming a norm of responsible research, making Open Science a fundamental component of African research will ensure that research outputs are firmly embedded within global research systems.

Open Data

The focus of this framework is particularly on incentivizing the sharing and re-use of research data. The scope of subsequent discussions thus narrows from Open Science broadly to Open Data. Nonetheless, it must be recognized that a large portion of the findings and conclusions identified in this framework are equally applicable to other areas of Open Science. Indeed, cross-over learning and best-practice identification between the different areas of Open Science is to be highly encouraged – and, of course, in keeping with the ethos of openness in research. This section describes the Open Data movement in more detail, as well as related concepts such as Research Data Management, FAIR data and “intelligent openness”.

The Open Knowledge Foundation defines Open Data as “data that can be freely used, shared and built-on by anyone, anywhere, for any purpose”.³ As a component of the Open Science movement, Open Data is motivated by the belief that research data are a common good whose use should be maximized for the benefit of society. It is dedicated towards ensuring that research data are freely available for re-use without restrictions from copyright, patents or other mechanisms of control.

³ <https://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>

The Open Data movement has evolved as a response to the digital revolution of recent decades. This has created an “unprecedented explosion in the capacity to acquire, store, manipulate and instantaneously transmit vast and complex data volumes” (International Council for Science *et al.*, 2015, p. 3). These changing practices of data production have ushered in an era of “Big Data” that is changing the face of research around the world. Moreover, the increasing sophistication of semantic search tools has led to an emerging reliance on “linked data”, whereby separate databases relating to a specific phenomenon are analysed for deeper relationships. Such techniques have proven incredibly important for interdisciplinary research by facilitating the interactions of different disciplines and data types.

Increasing access to, and re-use of, research data is recognized to have many benefits for all research stakeholders. These include:

- enhancing access to data to facilitate scrutiny, analysis and re-use
- improved visibility of research
- improving research efficiency and shortening timescales
- facilitating efforts to enhance reproducibility and verification
- improving researcher transparency and reducing fraud
- enabling inter-disciplinary and international collaborations
- ensuring maximal returns on the investment of funds in research (Tenopir *et al.*, 2011; Baker, 2016; Leonelli, 2017)

Like the other areas of Open Science, the Open Data movement is both an ideological commitment as well as practical innovations, and activities include the use of new digital tools, the development of specific sets of values, and/or practices of collaboration and sharing” (Leonelli, 2017, p. 4). As a result, Open Data activities can vary considerably. Some involve community-building activities that endorse the values of openness, transparency and reproducibility. Others are more practically-oriented, and focus on harnessing new digital tools to enhance data analysis, sharing and collaboration. In relation to the latter, Open Data activities are closely linked to discussions around research data management (RDM) , and more recently FAIR data principles (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016).

Research Data Management

RDM facilitates the “active management and appraisal of data over the lifecycle of scholarly and scientific interest” (Lee and Tibbo, 2007, p. no page). Key practices include data management planning, data creation, annotating and documenting data, analysis/use/versioning, storage and backup, publishing papers and data, preparing for deposit, archiving and sharing, licensing and citing. Modern RDM involves a wide range of new data tools, including version control software, online documentation tools such as e-lab notebooks, workflow tools. It also relies on a variety of online storage options, such as collaborative platforms, data specific platforms, 3rd party options, repositories and so forth. RDM also teaches how licenses such as Creative Commons can be used to improve the openness of research data.

RDM offers a number of benefits for both the researcher and secondary users of data. It enhances efficient and responsible research while increasing the visibility of individual researchers, improves research integrity and enables the re-use of data and promotes innovation. The recognition of how RDM adds value to the entire research has led to widespread support for teaching data management within academia. RDM is a fundamental component of Open Data activities, as it supports careful and considered data management and the use of tools promoting transparency, reproducibility and replicability.

FAIR Data

The concept of FAIR data arose out of RDM discussions, and denotes practices that render data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-useable (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016). A set of principles were launched in 2016 with the intention to assist both humans and machines “in their discovery of, access to, integration and analysis of, task-appropriate scientific data and their associated algorithms and workflows”.⁴ While FAIR data are not necessarily open data, the principles form the basis of understanding how data can be accessible, open and linked.

Intelligent Openness

RDM and FAIR play integral parts in the Open Data movement, as data can only become open when it has been generated, curated, stored and disseminated according to principles/practices that facilitate re-use. However, in contrast to RDM and FAIR data, Open Data has the added

⁴ www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples

requirement of being disseminated via platforms and licenses that enable free re-use. Truly open data needs to be freely available to everyone to use and republish as they wish, without restrictions from copyright, patents or other mechanisms of control.

Open Data must be “intelligently open” (Boulton *et al.*, 2012), meaning that they can be thoroughly scrutinised and appropriately re-used. “Intelligent” Open Data is best understood ensuring the production of high quality data that is reliable, authentic and of academic relevance (International Council for Science *et al.*, 2015). This stands in contrast to “data dumping” and the dissemination of data that cannot be effectively reused. Truly Open Data should meet a set of criteria, including being discoverable, accessible, intelligible, assessable, and usable. Moreover, data that are made open should satisfy ethical and legal obligations so as to ensure that they cause no harm when released and re-used. It is important to recognize that there is no “one size fits all” when it comes to data sharing practices, as these may vary considerably depending on the type and volume of data, as well as the existence of necessary ethical and legal restrictions.

Current Open Data activities range from education and the promotion of cultures of sharing, to RDM and standard setting. These activities include not only researchers, but also scientific publishers, research institutions, national governments and funders. Open Data activities have been widely endorsed by national governments around the world. Indeed, in 2004 science ministers from all nations of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) signed a declaration committing to ensuring that publicly funded archive data is publicly available (OECD, 2004). These activities form part of a wider commitment to Open Data within national governments and civil societies to enhance public accountability and economic growth.

Incentivizing Open Data Practices

As mentioned above, Open Science is rapidly becoming an integral element of responsible and reproducible research. Open Science, including Open Data, practices are becoming entrenched in community norms, funding requirements and institutional/national/publication requirements. Nonetheless, establishing openness as the default status for research requires considerable efforts – both to foster cultures of openness as well as to develop infrastructures

that support open practices. In both it is important to recognize the distinction between theoretical support and actual buy-in. In this section we briefly touch on the concept of “incentivizing” Open Data practices as a means of ensuring the latter.

A key aspect of the Open Data movement that is sometimes overlooked is that, for it to flourish, all users of data also need to be contributors. The Open Data movement will only flourish if everyone involved not only benefits from the available resources, but contributes data, code, expertise and support wherever possible. This rather self-evident obligation has strong moral underpinnings based on the egalitarian way in which Open Science activities are conceptualised.

Studies examining attitudes to openness highlight the critical distinction between “theoretical” and “actual” support for Open Data (Louise Bezuidenhout, Leonelli, *et al.*, 2017). Many researchers willingly support the concepts of Open Science and recognize the value of Open Data. However, when asked about the ways in which they implement openness within their own research they find explanations as to why they cannot. This “ideal/real” disjunction is common across countries and disciplines. When pressed, however, researchers name a range of different concerns – including lack of skills, lack of resources, fears of being “scooped”, and the absence of institutional support (Ferguson, 2014). Establishing cultures of data sharing – in Africa and more broadly – requires that practices of openness be appropriately incentivized so as to change behaviour.

Incentivising Open Data cultures within research communities requires two different sets of activities. First and foremost, there is a need to get buy-in from the academics and other research stakeholders regarding the value and importance of Open Data for the future of scientific research. These community-building activities involve education, outreach and discussion and focus on the benefits that Open Data offers for the future of responsible, reproducible and robust research and research systems. These community-building activities must operate on multiple levels, fostering both support and endorsement for the global Open Data community as well as a local understanding of how Open Data practices will be put into action within specific research environments.

Nonetheless, it is well-recognized that community-building activities are readily undermined by social, regulatory and physical problems within research environments. These problems act

as dis-incentives to the establishment of Open Data cultures and significantly hinder data sharing practices. It is important to note that such dis-incentivization can stifle Open Data practices even in situations where there is a lot of good will and buy-in from the local researcher community (Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2016; Louise Bezuidenhout, Leonelli, *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 3: Schematic representation of activities needed to establish local and international cultures of Open Data

Figure 4 above offers a schematic representation of these two sets of influence, and how these different areas of activity work in union to promote local and international cultures of Open Data. Such cultures can only be established and perpetuated when the multiple stakeholders involved in research data production commit to both promoting Open Data and removing barriers to practice. The preceding section identified justifications for the value of Open Data practices. The following section discusses some of the dis-incentives that need to be addressed in order for such cultures to flourish.

Challenges for Implementing Open Data Practices

Researchers around the world highlight concerns about being “scooped” as one of the main barriers against Open Data and data sharing practices. The possibility that they might lose out on the opportunity to publish the data they generate is a major disincentive for researchers – even those who are theoretically supportive of the Open Data ideal. This concern, and the importance that it is afforded by the research community, is intimately linked to the way that current research systems are structured and the primacy afforded to the academic journal article.

Many proponents of Open Science suggest that the benefits of openness outweigh the dangers of “scooping”. They draw attention to the increased citation rates of Open Access publications, the enhanced re-use of open data sets, and the visibility gained from sharing other open resources (Eysenbach, 2006; MacCallum and Parthasarathy, 2006; Peters *et al.*, 2015). Nonetheless, concerns about “scooping” are deeply entrenched in research communities around the world, and appeals to the benefits of openness do not necessarily overcome them. Complicated relationships between researchers and their data (ownership, secrecy, credit and power) are embedded within the current cultures of research. Thus, fears of scooping should not be trivialized, and represent a very real reality to researchers (Bezuidenhout, 2018). This section examines some of the structures of research systems that continue to foster concerns about “scooping”.

Evaluation and Credit Systems

Evaluation systems play an important role in academia, influencing research practices and cultures. Most evaluation systems currently in use focus on academic journal articles – the quantity produced during a given timeframe, where they are published and how often they are cited by other researchers. The use of such metrics is coming under increasing criticism, as concerns are raised about the marginalization of other key academic activities such as teaching and mentoring. These metrics also place exceptional pressure on academics to perform within a specific sphere, leading to the development of cultures of “publish or perish”.

Despite the growing awareness of the limitations of these publication-focused metrics, and the negative cultures that they engender, academia has been slow to change evaluation systems. It is likely that this apathy is in part due to conservatism within academia, particularly within institutional bureaucracy and senior academics. Similarly, it is possible that the rapid pace at which data sharing tools and the online landscape have evolved have meant that many of the individuals who should be scrutinizing evaluation systems are unable to do so.

Supporters of the Open Data community highlight that paper-focused metrics overlook key data sharing practices as well as those supporting Open Science more generally. As a result, through their influence on research evaluation, university rankings and promotion criteria, publication-focused metrics undermine Open Data practices. Indeed, researchers who choose to commit time and financial resources to open practices often need to do so without any recognition from their institutions. In the highly competitive world of modern academia, this can place them at a disadvantage to colleagues engaged in more traditional research dissemination strategies. These disadvantages will undoubtedly be exacerbated as academia becomes increasingly competitive.

The impact of publication-focused metrics on data sharing practices extends beyond direct disincentivization. As resources, jobs and promotions are accessed predominantly via publication outputs, researchers are extremely aware of the dangers of being “scooped” by their peers. Indeed, losing out on the ability to capitalize on their research products via paper production is a key concern for researchers regardless of discipline or nationality (Ferguson, 2014). Moreover, the unrelenting pressure to produce published outputs further disinclines researchers to commit scarce time and financial resources to preparing data for deposition online (Edwards *et al.*, 2011).

Publication-focused metrics are heavily used within African academia as a means of evaluation. Indeed, in many research institutions paper publications are one of few – or the sole – criteria determining promotion. Predictably, empirical studies have shown that the pressure to publish in peer-reviewed journals influences perceptions of Open Data amongst African academics, making them disinclined to disseminate data until they had exhausted publication possibilities (Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2016).

Authorship

Effective data sharing practices are increasingly reliant on a wide range of skills, including computing expertise and data curation. Despite the expanding range of actors involved in data analysis, traditions for attributing authorship on academic publications has not kept pace with these developments. As a result, the contributions – particularly technical – of some academics are consistently undervalued, making them less willing to engage in future projects. The current paucity of appropriate and standardized systems of crediting that adequately reflect academic activities can thus undermine data sharing and Open Data activities.

The concerns about attributing credit in publications become even more complicated when one considers the secondary re-use of data. Any effective data sharing activities “creates an obligation for the original investigators who obtain funding, design studies, collect and analyze data, and publish results to make their curated data and associated metadata available to third parties” (Bierer, Crosas and Pierce, 2017, p. 1684). Thus, it is important to ensure that these activities are recognized in any publications making use of the original data. More effort is needed to develop appropriate and standardized crediting systems that can be used for academic advancement, for grant applications, and in broader situation. This is of particular importance when one considers the increasingly interdisciplinary and international milieu of modern science.

In addition to more general authorship concerns, African academics are also influenced by historic examples of poor collaborative research with the Global North. Commonly termed “parachute research” (Heymann, Liu and Lillywhite, 2016), this refers to collaborative situations in which African contributors were excluded from credit for their work on international projects. This has led to longstanding distrust, which heightens concerns about loss of control of data and lack of credit for academic contributions.

Shortage of Resources

Data sharing activities require resources. Preparing data for deposition, in particular cleaning and annotating, are time-consuming activities for researchers. Storing and curating data require physical infrastructures, and data repositories require long-term curation. Developing institutional practices of RDM and data sharing requires the coordinated activities of a wide range of actors, including library staff, technical support staff and data scientists. All in all, for

effective data sharing to occur, institutions need to create physical and regulatory conditions that reduce the burden of such activities on researchers (Crosas, 2011).

Discussions as to who is financially responsible for supporting Open Data – both institutionally and nationally – are complicated. Vested interests, priorities and constraints need to be clearly and pragmatically addressed in order to reach understandings between institutions, funders, industrial partners and society. Such discussions are particularly important when considering longer term support for Open Data. In particular, this relates to issues of longevity (maintenance and curation of data assets) and development (supporting, developing and updating ICT infrastructures). At the moment, funding for data sharing activities varies considerably, and many research grants continue to lack dedicated funds for Open Data activities.

Shortages of dedicated resources for data sharing activities, together with concerns about the longevity of digital repositories (Tenopir *et al.*, 2011; Leonelli, Spichtinger and Prainsack, 2013) are significant barriers to the evolution of Open Data practices. Within African academia, the impact of resource limitations are further exacerbated. Low levels of project funding, poorly financed research institutions and low national investment in ICT infrastructures all combine to challenge data sharing activities. Indeed, these severe resource constraints can often make data sharing activities appear more like an ideal than an achievable practice (L. Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2017; Louise Bezuidenhout, Leonelli, *et al.*, 2017).

The challenges that low-resourced settings pose to data sharing practices are further compounded by the design of the Open Data tools themselves. Open Data implementation has been noted to focus predominantly on high-resourced, and internationally well-recognized research environments (Leonelli, 2017). As a result, many of the resultant tools are designed with a high-resourced setting in mind. This leads to issues such as the dominance of English as the user language, the use of graphic-intensive platforms that may be inaccessible in low-bandwidth environments, and reliance of expensive proprietary software. These characteristics can serve as significant deterrents to data sharing activities by African scientists (L. Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2017).

Lack of Awareness, Skill Shortages and Shortage of Training

In many discussions about Open Data there is a characteristic “ideal/real” gap between theoretical support for openness in research and a personal commitment to actual data sharing activities. The existence of this “ideal/real” gap is often due to a lack of awareness of what Open Data actually constitutes. Despite concerted efforts to raise awareness about Open Data issues, there remains considerable confusion within the global research community about “what openness means in practice, what options are available to implement it, what is legal, what is recommended by funders, learned societies, publishers, research institutions and governmental bodies, and whether such recommendations are compatible with one another” (Leonelli, 2017, p. 10). Such confusion is further compounded by the recognized semantic ambiguity of the concept of openness, whereby openness is described in a variety of ways by different stakeholders.⁵ Similarly, different disciplines and epistemic communities have highly varied attitudes to openness (Levin *et al.*, 2016).

In addition to the confusion as to the nature of Open Data, the ideal/real gap is exacerbated by a widespread absence of training in RDM and associated data science skills, particularly on the African continent. Indeed, for data sharing to be embedded in research, training needs to be embedded in research methods (Van Den Eynden and Bishop, 2014). Researchers need to be able to use a variety of tools needed to successfully manage and share data, as well as the increasing range of resources available online. In many cases, this extends to library and IT support staff who are unable to offer necessary assistance due to their own lack of training in these areas.

Diversity of Practices and Policies

It has been widely recognized that research data is extremely heterogeneous, and that there can be no “one size that fits all” when it comes to data sharing practices (International Council for Science *et al.*, 2015). Recognizing this diversity is key to creating appropriate data sharing practices within subdomains and researcher communities, and is vital for developing regulatory guidance to assist researchers. Indeed, as recognised by van den Eynden and Bishop, “formal

⁵⁵ As described by Leonelli (2017, 13): openness can mean different things to different stakeholders, and is associated with ideas as different as “free of license”, “free of ownership”, “under CC-BY license”, “common good”, “good enough to share”, “unrestricted access and/or use”, or “accessible without payment”, to name by a few existing interpretations (Grubb and Easterbrook, 2011)

data sharing policies [are needed] as long as they do not interfere with informal sharing and are sensitive to variations across disciplines” (Van Den Eynden and Bishop, 2014, p. 5)

Further adding to the confusion is the issue of the “long tail” data of research. ‘Big science’ efforts are not the only drivers of data-sharing needs. As RDM highlights, researchers are confronted with ever-increasing volumes of data generated during daily research. Sharing these richly diverse and heterogeneous small data sets, the so-called “long tail” data, is important for collaborations and reproducibility. Nevertheless, achieving consensus on how to assign utility of these data, as well properly understanding the diversity of repositories sharing tools necessary for effective dissemination are topics requiring further scrutiny (Ferguson *et al.*, 2014).

Intellectual Property Concerns

Intellectual property regimes play an important role in mediating knowledge production, both in public and private research organizations. Indeed, intellectual property has become a major financing stream for many academic institutions. Nonetheless, whilst research institutions are beginning to aggressively pursue copyrights and patents, many researchers remain confused about how intellectual property applies to their research (Borgman, 2012). This confusion is undoubtedly compounded by the complexities of institutional, national and international intellectual property regimes. As a result, researchers may be subject to multiple responsibilities to their institutions, funders, governments and so forth – something that is even more complicated in cases of international collaboration. These responsibilities do not always reconcile, leaving researchers exposed to conflicting requirements that disincline them to risk sharing research outputs.

Issues of intellectual property also extend to academic publishing. Many publishing companies have complicated licensing contracts that make researchers fearful to engage with altmetric sharing practices. Similarly, many researchers have little experience with – or understanding of – licensing models that support Open Science, such as Creative Commons.

For African researchers, intellectual property issues are compounded by a number of distinct challenges. First and foremost, in many countries the intellectual property landscape surrounding research outputs is incomplete or emerging, which offers little protection to

researchers wishing to protect their knowledge outputs. Similarly, many institutions do not have dedicated staff to offer intellectual property advice, meaning that researchers have to navigate complicated legal landscapes alone.

Intellectual property issues also contribute to concerns about scooping in two different ways. In a qualitative study of scientists in Kenya and South Africa, Bezuidenhout and colleagues reported how researchers were unwilling to share data due to their perceptions that their institutions and national intellectual property regulations would not be able to sufficiently protect them against data theft or misuse (Louise Bezuidenhout, Leonelli, *et al.*, 2017). Many of the scientists interviewed felt that their institutions would not have the resources to challenge potentially negative actions from research group from a high-resourced, foreign institution.

Another complicating factor for African researchers relates to the widespread tendency of researchers using personal funds to finance research activities. Many researchers make the decisions to invest their personal money into their research career strategically, with clear expectations of promotion (via publication) or intellectual patent rewards (L. Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2017; Louise Bezuidenhout, Leonelli, *et al.*, 2017). These personal investments significantly influence attitudes to openness and sharing, and present challenges to nascent Open Data cultures.

Ethical Concerns

Although openness is desirable as the default position for publicly-funded research, it is well-recognized that full disclosure is not always possible. Indeed, there are legitimate exceptions to openness – particularly within medical research – relating to privacy, safety and security (Kaye *et al.*, 2009; Knoppers *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, whilst paywalls and data embargoes are to be discouraged, research that is funded by, or intended for, commercial exploitation can require IP protection

Engaging in data sharing practices thus has the potential not only to exacerbate existing ethical concerns, but also raise new ones. For many researchers, navigating the complexities of ethical, legal and funding commitments can be very challenging and can cause them to err on the side of caution and not share data. The sustained discussion around issues such as privacy,

data ownership and informed consent continue to stand as evidence of the complexities of these topics (Kaye *et al.*, 2009, 2018; Knoppers *et al.*, 2011).

The Open Data milieu also raises new ethical problems that require constant attention. In particular, the implications of unanticipated data re-use, the impact of linking disparate data sets, big-data mining and the use of surveillance technologies and artificial intelligence all raise important ethical concerns. While many researchers recognize that their work may have ethical implications, training in ethics of data usage is not widespread. Furthermore, training in ethics as well as the review of projects by research ethics committees is commonly limited to researchers working with human or animal subjects. Many for many other researchers there is a justified feeling of being underprepared and ill-equipped to deal with the ethical complexities of data sharing.

Additional Challenges Constraining the Development of Cultures of Open Data in African Research

Research institutions across the African continent vary considerably in terms of resource provision and socio-historical factors. Nonetheless, despite this variability, an increasing number of empirical studies (Harle, 2010; Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2016) are identifying a number of characteristics that could be represent the norm for many institutions. Many of these characteristics have implications for the establishment of Open Data cultures on the continent.

Enhanced Infrastructural Challenges

Research progress in an era of Big Data is critically dependent on infrastructure, notably broadband infrastructure, and access to it. Similarly, the ability to engage in Open Data practices is fundamentally linked to stable, reliable and affordable internet. Africa has enormous infrastructure gaps, including broadband infrastructure, and access to broadband services, where they exist, is also very expensive (Economic Commission for Africa, 2017). Moreover, personal connectivity costs remain extremely high in most African countries (Alliance for Affordable Internet, 2017). Issues of connectivity are further complicated by ageing and unreliable power infrastructures and frequent power outages. These issues are covered in more detail in an accompanying AOSP framework report.

Lack of Hardware and Software

Availability of up-to-date ICT hardware and proprietary research software is problematic for many researchers in Africa (Harle, 2010; Louise Bezuidenhout, Leonelli, *et al.*, 2017; Vermeir *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, the cost of purchasing regular software updates is often viewed as prohibitive (L. Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2017). Due to these challenges, the use of pirated software, older versions of software or free trial software are all commonly used. Interestingly, a recent survey suggested that the use of Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) is not widespread within many research communities in Nigeria and Ghana (Vermeir *et al.*, 2018). It is highly likely that this is the case in many other African countries as well.

Research Cultures

Recent empirical studies have started to generate descriptive data on African research systems (Harle, 2010; Tousignant, 2013; Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2016). These studies have begun to show how the historic legacy and sustained resource constraints within these systems shape research cultures. These are grouped in table 1 below.

Area of impact	Specific challenge
Low interaction with Open Data discussions by African researchers	Lack of traditions of openness within work cultures and conservative/traditional academic systems
	Limited engagement of African scientists in Open Data discussions (particularly outside of research networks and centres of excellence)
	Languages – dominance of English in Open Data discussions can marginalise non-native English speakers
Complicated ethical and legal frameworks	Patchy ethics training for RCR and shortage of ethics instructors
	Absent or incomplete data regulations and ethical guidelines
	Absence of coherent institutional and national IP strategies
	Conflicting or incomplete institutional, funder and national data sharing strategies
	Limited engagement of academia in national policy and governance

Lack of positive examples of open African research	Perceptions of scooping and evidence base dominated by negative, rather than positive, examples
	Concerns about citation, credit and attribution
Skill shortages	Shortage of data science skills
	Shortages in training for RDM and FAIR. Prevailing lack of funds/support for “soft skills” training and lack of support for social science input in data activities
	Existing skill shortages in technical support, library services and data management/curators
Financial barriers	Scarcity of research funds and use of personal funds to generate data
	Costs of hardware and software needed to support data sharing
Utility of data	Available data not aligned with research interests
	Small size of datasets generated
Infrastructural challenges	Brain drain and loss of expertise

Table 1: Challenges to Open Data relating to research cultures

Summarizing the Current “Lay of the Land” in Africa

Activities such as the AOSP demonstrate the considerable good will towards Open Data within the African research community. This good will is underpinned by a recognition of the benefits of open data, the value of openness within research systems and the manner in which openness enacts key responsibilities to society. Open Data also represents a new vision for African research, whereby resources can be effectively shared so as to foster a globally competitive, yet distinctly African, style of research. It is likely that widespread support for the Open Data movement can be garnered by capitalizing on this vision, tapping into both high-level and individual support. Making Open Data a topic of discussion will create a “ripple effect” that spreads throughout research communities on the continent.

Nonetheless, relying on good will and interest is not sufficient, and many challenges need to be addressed before Open Data becomes embedded in research cultures. As described in the

previous section, many of these are challenges faced by research communities around the world. African research systems also have a set of additional challenges relating to resource-limitations, historical legacies shaping academic systems, and key skill shortages. These will all need to be carefully considered in order to ensure that Open Data incentivization activities are ineffective.

While such challenges may seem daunting, overcoming them must be inevitable. As highlighted in the AOSP Vision Document (V02), a failure to embrace Open Science will cause research systems to “risk stagnating in a scientific backwater, isolated from creative streams of social, cultural and economic opportunity” (African Open Science Platform, 2018, p. 4). The report goes on to highlight that “a country that fails to develop its own capacities will inevitably become dependent upon skills bought in from elsewhere as a passive and ill-informed consumer of expensive data services, lacking the creativity to thrive in a fast-changing world” (African Open Science Platform, 2018, p. 6).

Establishing cultures of Open Data in Africa represents an exciting time for African research. Research stakeholders are offered a unique opportunity to develop a coordinated and comprehensive strategy for embedding openness in research in a manner that represents the priorities and preferences of the African continent. The excitement at this opportunity is echoed in the AOSP Vision Document (V02), which says “Africa should adapt, but in its own way, and as a leader not a follower, with its own broader, more societally-engaged priorities” (African Open Science Platform, 2018, p. 4).

Purpose of Framework

The purpose of this framework is to identify ways in which Open Data practices can be incentivized within African science. This framework identifies multiple stakeholders involved in African science, including researchers, academic institutions, funding bodies, publishers and national governments. It offers specific areas in which these different stakeholders can be incentivized to support Open Data.

In order to identify the activities that can affect short, medium and long-term changes in data sharing behaviour, the framework begins by identifying key resources/inputs available that will support data sharing activities. It also outlines existing challenges/constraints inherent within the African research landscape that will need to be addressed or ameliorated in order to safeguard a long-term culture of Open Data. The different elements of the framework are represented in figure 4. These different elements will be discussed in detail in the remaining document.

Figure 4: Schematic overview of incentivization framework

Scope and Limitations of Framework

This framework particularly takes a very broad view of what constitutes research data. In keeping with recent reports such as *Open Data in a Big Data World*, the term “data” is defined according to Christine Borgman’s interpretation as “representations of observations, objects and other entities used as evidence of phenomena for the purpose of research or scholarship” (Borgman, 2015, p. 28). In taking such a broad view, the framework does not deal with the specific challenges associated with certain types of data, such as the ethical issues associated

with sharing medical data. Instead, the framework operates as a general pathway towards incentivising data sharing that needs to be contextualized according to disciplinary, institutional and national contexts.

It is important to recognize, however, that the ethical and practical issues experienced by discrete disciplinary and national communities of researchers offer important learning opportunities for strengthening practices across the continent, as well as refining this framework. It is anticipated that this framework will offer a starting point from which mutual learning discussions can originate.

Existing Assets for Developing Cultures of Open Data in African Science

There are a range of resources available to African researchers, institutions and governments interested in fostering Open Data activities. These can be broadly divided into three key areas: usable resources, good will and expertise.

Usable resources

Establishing Open Data practices within a research setting involve a diverse range of activities, including community building, skill training and technical support. This can often seem daunting to those who would undertake the task. Luckily, however, there are a wide range of materials available online that can be used as a basis for designing strategies. One need not “reinvent the wheel”, so to speak. These resources include:

- Extensive array of teaching material for Open Science (ie. fosteropenscience.eu) and RDM (ie. dcc.ac.uk/resources)
- Active international associations, including the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and CODATA, that can be approached for expertise and support
- Availability of Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) for use in data processing and analysis

Good will

The importance of good will as an integral aspect of sustainable Open Data activities should not be minimized. Indeed, good will – from researchers, funders, publishers and institutions –

plays a crucial role in decisions to allocate funding, invest time and expertise. It also underpins willingness to support changes to existing research practices and cultures. Fortunately, there is currently considerable good will towards establishing cultures of Open Data in Africa. Key stakeholders include:

- Studies have shown that there is considerable support for Open Data values within African research communities (Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2016)
- Growing commitment from national research organizations – including South Africa draft White Paper on Science, Technology and Innovation (Department of Science and Technology, 2018)
- Inclusive culture of global Open Data community and commitment to supporting African researchers
- Growing amount of regional and international funding to support developing Open Data infrastructures and improve data science skill sets

Expertise

Data sharing is not a new topic for many African researchers and research groups. These experts represent a valuable resource that can be leveraged on for both insights and examples of successful data sharing. Key groups could include:

- AOSP governance panel – including AAU, ARUA, AAS, AIMS, SKA, NASAC, DIRISA, NRENs
- Other well-established African research networks – including MalariaGen and H3Africa
- Other Open Science communities, such as Software/Data Carpentry and Africa Open Science Hardware
- Publishing and curatorial expertise – including DHET journals, institutional repositories, African-specific repositories

Constraints and Context

Incentivizing Open Data practices is recognized to be challenging, and studies from around the world have identified a range of contextual issues that can undermine open practices. These include lack of expertise or cultures of sharing, concerns about “scooping and loss of credit”, and regulatory disincentives. Moreover, as described above, Open Data practices are further

obfuscated in an African context by low existing Open Data awareness and a paucity of cultures of data sharing.

Incentivizing Open Data practices in Africa, are also complicated by the challenges relating to conducting research in low-resourced environments, and by the complicated historical legacies associated with these research systems. Each of these issues is extremely complicated, and how they interact with research practices, data sharing and Open Science could be the subject of stand-alone reports. Unfortunately, this framework is constrained to mentioning them only in the broadest of terms. Moreover, by attempting to be applicable to African research in general, the framework also has to overlook the considerable diversity within African research contexts. Nonetheless, it is hoped that users will be able to identify their specific contextual challenges within this generalized overview.

Activities to Build Awareness and Foster Cultures of Open Data

Establishing Open Data practices amongst African research requires openness becomes a core value of research cultures. In order to do so, a *cultural shift* is needed to foster buy-in from all stakeholder communities. As mentioned above, awareness of Open Science and Open Data is relatively low amongst African research stakeholders. In order for Open Data activities to become integrated into African research cultures there needs to be widespread buy-in from individual researchers. This buy-in needs to be both theoretical support as well as practical action, whereby researchers are committed to enacting the values of Open Data within their daily research practices.

Key interventions required to address this are awareness raising activities, and the initiatives that highlight the value of data sharing activities. Such interventions can be conceptualized on a timeline, ranging from those that can be acted on immediately to those requiring further preparation. These are represented in table 2 below, and discussed in the sections below.

Timescale	Scope	Types of activities
Short-term	Raise awareness of Open Data amongst African research stakeholders	Workshops and capacity building initiated variously by researchers, institutions, governments and NRENs
	Foster Pragmatic Discussions About Challenges and Ethical Concerns	Formal workshops and informal discussions in situ. Anonymous help lines.
	Engage all potential data users problematizing Open Data discussions	Disciplinary discussion forums
	Promote understandings of data collections as assets	Workshops with institutions and funders
Mid-term	Collect positive examples of Open Data “champions” and visible success stories	National scoping exercises
	Encourage Open Data activities within institutions	Institutional commitment
	Develop informal as well as formal Open Data cultures	Researchers and PIs establish activities in their research groups
Long-term	Ensure that all research stakeholders are involved in data policy development	National engagement

	Integrate RDM, Open Data and data science skills into teaching	Institutional commitment
	Engage the public in Open Data activities	Institutional and national public engagement activities

Table 2 Range of activities to foster cultures of Open Data

Raise Awareness of the Open Data Amongst African Research Stakeholders

While interest in Open Data is growing rapidly, it remains a new topic for many African researcher stakeholders. Even within African research institutions, dedicated Open Data training within remains relatively patchy and unstandardized. Similarly, related topics such as data sharing, RDM and FAIR data are not systematically taught. One of the most fundamental elements needed for establishing cultures of Open Data in Africa is therefore the need for Open Data awareness-raising amongst researchers, institutional governance, funders and national science bodies.

Such training should introduce the concepts of Open Science and Open Data and highlight the important role that openness plays in the future of African research. While the range, scope and depth of Open Data courses can vary considerably, it is important that all courses cover the values and norms of Open Science, the responsibilities of being an Open Scientist, and the contextual/national/international resources that the student may draw on to engage in the Open Data movement.

While Open Data courses will need to be established from scratch in many research settings, it is important to recognize that the curriculum need not be. There is a growing amount of online resources that can be harnessed by African Open Data instructors. The ability to harness and adapt these online resources will not only streamline the roll-out of these teaching activities, but ensure that the content is aligned with that taught in other research communities around the world. This will undoubtedly strengthen the links between the fledgling African Open Data communities and their international counterparts and enable the mutual exchange of good practice and expertise.

Key online resources could include educational platforms (ie. fosteropenscience.eu and mantra.edina.ac.uk) and online MOOCs (opensciencemooc.eu) provide access to established course material. Moreover, many international organizations (ie. CODATA, RDA, Data/Software Carpentry) can be approached for support with developing more hands-on training workshops and train-the-trainer activities. Similarly, many African research networks have made important strides in establishing good data sharing practices and community commitments to Open Data. These research networks, including H3Africa and the SKA, provide considerable expertise and resources that can guide future endeavours.

It is important, however, to counter this with a caution. Time- and resource-limitations often make it tempting to adopt Open Data policies/training wholesale from other institutions. It is important to recognize that these trainings may not necessarily be appropriate for immediate use within a specific context due to focus, language, case studies/examples and so forth. Taking the time to trouble-shooting and contextualizing course content will ensure optimal impact.

Key objective: roll-out awareness raising workshops amongst all data stakeholders

Key challenges and potential solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
Need for financial resources to be committed to preparing and rolling out Open Data training	Availability of online resources can offset costs of developing new training from scratch
Lack of experienced and enthusiastic trainers	The international Open Data community can be leveraged to provide support for trainers. Roll out train-the-trainer activities
Lack of networks of support for individual educators to share good practice experiences	NRENS and national research networks can provide the support and connection between Open Data teachers
Potential need for different styles of instruction – particularly for practical training – to facilitate differing levels of ICT expertise, different data community requirements and different career trajectories	Online resources may provide useful tools to ensure the curriculum is flexible

Table 3 Key challenges and solutions for establishing Open Data awareness-raising activities

Contextualise Open Data Discussions and Engage All Potential Data Users

It is widely recognized that there is no “one size fits all” approach to data sharing due to the considerable variations in the types of data generated during research projects (International Council for Science *et al.*, 2015). Similarly, there is no single way in which commitments to Open Data are enacted within specific research communities, whose practices may be influenced by social, regulatory, political and physical factors. Open Data practices that are contextually-appropriate can be anticipated to have the greatest buy-in from user communities. African research systems need Open Data practices that have been developed in, by and for the researchers in these contexts.

African research networks represent an untapped source of expertise for data sharing in context. Researchers have first-hand understandings of their community’s data needs, expectations and traditions. They also have extensive knowledge of the *in situ* challenges they face as data sharers, users and re-users. If these disparate sources of expertise are brought together and encouraged to share experiences, it can be anticipated that many potentially-overlooked challenges can easily be identified and addressed.

As user communities develop it is envisioned that they will start to evolve data sharing practices that are best suited to the data, discipline and contextual settings. These community activities will become extremely influential in driving forward the evolving discussion about openness within an African context. It is very important that researchers and institutions critically evaluate the discourse driving forward the movement to ensure that it reflects the priorities, needs and challenges of African STI activities. Indeed, failure to understand tensions and pressures – particularly from environment – may have a detrimental effect on good will and undermine any community-building activities (Bezuidenhout, 2015).

If researchers are expected to be open about the practical and ethical challenges they face when sharing data, they must feel safe to do so. Raising concerns about data sharing means that researchers must relate sensitive information relating to their research environment, colleagues and regulatory systems. For many, raising such concerns is perceived as risky, and they fear negative repercussion such as institutional disapproval, peer fall-out and funding being

withdrawn. If cultures of openness are to be effectively established within African research institutions, it is important that systems are developed whereby researchers are able to ask for help, support and advice on sensitive data-related issues.

Key objective: establish inter-stakeholder dialogue about data sharing practices and constraints within disciplinary communities

Key challenges and potential solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
Siloed research stakeholders	NRENs and national science bodies are well-positioned to make connections between data communities
Resistance from older academics – particularly those with lower ICT skills	Older academics can be paired with younger ones for mutually beneficial skill development
Suspicion between data communities and research institutions	Funders, research institutions and governments can make engagement a priority
Researchers fear possible punitive damage from raising data sharing concerns	Establish systems to enable confidential discussions of concerns. This could take the form of an institutional or national “help line”.

Table 4 Key challenges and solutions for establishing inter-stakeholder dialogue about data sharing practices and constraints within disciplinary communities

Promote Understandings of Data Collections as Assets

It is well-recognized that establishing robust RDM systems and data infrastructures requires financial investment. Similarly, as this framework elucidates, ensuring that research outputs comply with FAIR/Open Data standards also requires a commitment of financial, time and human resources. It is important that these resources commitments are not overlooked. Many institutions – particularly those with limited resources – may be loath to divert resources away

from seemingly “more important” applications, such as funding teaching or maintaining physical infrastructures.

Recognizing the “resource calculations” that go into rolling out Open Data initiatives highlights the importance of engaging research institutions, funders and governments in Open Data discussions. While Open Data may not yield immediate and obvious financial returns, becoming a recognized FAIR/Open Data producer and curator has a number of identifiable benefits for institutions. Well-curated data collections can serve as an asset to attract funding and collaboration, while increasing institutional visibility in the global research landscape. Moreover, the re-use of institutionally-held datasets will improve citation rates and improve the institutional presence within academic literature.

Getting institutions to see value in datasets as the next “special collection” requires high-level buy-in and the commitment of resources. It also requires training and support of library staff and other individuals involved in data curation, and engaging these technical experts is vital for success. When planning the roll-out of enhanced institutional data management there are a number of tools that institutions can draw on. In particular, Data Asset Frameworks provide institutions with the means to identify, locate, describe and assess how they are managing their research data assets.⁶

Key objective: change institutional thinking to view data management and curation as asset-generating activities

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
Institutions hesitant to commit funds to data management and curation	Engage institutional management in workshops detailing the benefits to be accrued from FAIR/Open data collections
Institutional library staff unable to support enhanced data management plans	Run courses for library and IT staff to upskill key individuals. This could be done by institutional, national research departments, NREN or non-governmental organizations

⁶ Such as <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/tools/data-asset-framework> and <https://www.data-audit.eu/>

Staff unwilling (or unaware) to use new data management systems	Ensure that research staff are engaged in the development and roll-out of any systems to ensure that the systems are user-friendly and reflect researcher priorities
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Table 5 Key challenges and solutions for changing institutional thinking to view data management and curation as asset-generating activities

Collect and Curate Positive Examples of “Open Data Champions”

In many discussions about implementing Open Data practices – both in Africa and beyond – there is an unequal focus on the negative outcomes of data sharing, such as being “scooped”. As researchers are under considerable pressure to forge academic careers for themselves, such concerns should not be minimized. However, it is important to recognize that such concerns are not necessarily countered by appeals to the ethical importance of Open Data (Bezuidenhout, 2018). Instead, what is needed are practical examples of how Open Data has added value to individual researcher’s career trajectories.

At the moment, however, there is little in the way of case studies or champions to offer these positive alternatives – particularly in an African research context. Practices of openness, with their focus on collegiality and community, offer an alternative vision of research that could serve as an important counter to the current status quo. Collating a set of case studies on positive data sharing experiences will not only serve as a teaching tool, but also as a means of career guidance for researchers wishing to make Open Data a core element of their research agendas. A network of champions will also serve to disseminate good practices, learning experiences and support between communities of scientists.

It is important that these networks of champions represent all groups of stakeholders from all levels of the career trajectory. Champions are most effective when they are relatable, and eminent professors may sometimes be too far removed from personal contexts to be optimally relevant as a role model. Community members are often best-placed to identify these Open Data champions and should be encouraged to do so. These Open Data champions can serve not only to promote Open Data activities in their context, but also be case studies exemplifying the positive impact of openness practices on research.

Key objective: collect positive examples of Open Data “champions” who have benefitted from prioritizing openness in their research

Key challenges and potential solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
Scope of champions selected not reflective of research communities	Ensure that champions represent the “average” researcher, and not just well-established, internationally-recognized ones
Narratives from champions highlight insufficiencies in current data infrastructures	Ensure that any findings of problems are fed back to appropriate source. Use narratives from champions as opportunity to strengthen data infrastructures.
Persistent concerns about scooping outweighing positive examples	Ensure that the positive examples are discussed in class to make sure that any additional concerns are identified and addressed

Table 6 Key challenges and solutions for developing positive examples of Open Data “champions” who have benefitted from prioritizing openness in their research

Encourage a Range of Open Science/Open Data Activities

As discussed in the introduction, Open Science as a movement includes the use of new digital tools, the adoption of specific values, and the establishment of different practices of collaboration and sharing (Leonelli, 2017, p. 4). It is therefore important to recognize that establishing Open Data cultures within African research requires a range of different activities that speak to these different facets of Open Science. While once-off workshops may serve the purpose of awareness-raising, they cannot be relied upon to initiate the cultural shift necessary for embedding Open Data practices *in situ*.

There is a vast body of literature that deals with the establishment of workplace cultures that will provide valuable insights for efforts to develop Open Data cultures. This literature highlights the importance of developing social systems that actively support ethical and legal

conduct, safeguarding individuals from a state of social disequilibrium and “anomie” (Merton, 1964; Cohen, 1993; Chambliss, 1996). These studies highlight how workplace cultures can be actively positively and negatively influenced by social structures, regulations and informal collegial practices. These issues should be carefully considered by institutions wishing to embed Open Data practices in their workplaces.

- careful assessment of current working environment to identify social, regulatory and physical barriers to Open Data practices (Louise Bezuidenhout, Leonelli, *et al.*, 2017)
- investment in a combination of Open Data activities ranging including discussions, skills development
- link Open Data to networking and public engagement activities
- embed Open Data in institutional definitions of “responsible research”
- make openness an aspirational character trait for institutional staff and students

Key objectives: to ensure that Open Data becomes part of institutional cultures

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
Lack of long-term investment and buy-in from host institutions	Establish support systems within governmental and non-governmental bodies
“Reinventing the wheel” – institutions developing practices and programmers in isolation	Foster learning networks between institutions to circulate learning experiences and best practices
Negative behaviours perpetuated <i>in situ</i> due to staff being unwilling to report concerns	Establish anonymous avenues for reporting concerns. Encourage transparency in processes of dealing with concerns.

Figure 5 Key challenges and solutions to ensuring that Open Data becomes part of institutional cultures

Develop Informal Cultures of Open Data in Research Environments

Informal mentor/student and peer/peer learning interactions play an important role in tertiary education and continuous learning. Most researchers will learn a considerable part of their data management practices from these informal interactions. It is therefore of considerable importance that they are taken into account when considering how best to establish cultures of Open Data *in situ*.

As members of a research community, researchers have an obligation to upholding the agreed standards and values of the Open Data community, and to ensure that available data are properly credited and ethically re-used. However, as colleagues, mentors and teachers, they have a responsibility towards fostering Open Data awareness and practices within their own research communities, and engaging in support and advocacy for the global movement.

Individual researchers play an important role in fostering enthusiasm amongst unconvinced colleagues, institutions and national governments. There are many concrete ways in which this can be done, including:

- Being the enthusiast: engaging in discussions with staff and students about the importance of Open Data and how practices can be practically implemented within specific research environments
- Practicing what is preached: sharing teaching materials and resources on Open Data via open repositories
- Prioritizing it for students: making RDM a priority for staff and students and support efforts
- “Open door” as well as Open Data: always being willing to discuss Open Data issues or help with data sharing challenges. Existing concerns regarding scooping, unethical data re-use and lack of crediting/attribution are best addressed with a combination of pragmatic conversation and examples of good practice.

Key objective: to establish informal cultures of Open Data within work groups

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
Older researchers unwilling to support Open Data activities within their research groups	Institutions and national organizations can develop teaching and support specifically for older researchers

Researchers feel overburdened with additional Open Data duties	Establish support networks (via NRENs and national academies) that offer training, webinars and advice for researchers
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Table 7 Key challenges and solutions for establishing informal cultures of Open Data within work groups

Ensure That All Research Stakeholders are Involved in Data Policy Development

Openness is rapidly becoming a core value for the international research community. For example, the recent launch of “Plan S” by Science Europe committed all European Union Member States to making all publicly funded research Open Access by 2020 (Science Europe, 2018). Similarly, multiple funders, journals and research consortia are supporting Open Data with data sharing mandates.

While communication channels between these different research stakeholders are well-established in the Global North, this not necessarily the case for many African countries. Indeed, many African academic communities have little engagement with policy makers, (inter)national funders and publishers and civil society. Overcoming this siloeing of expertise can have significant implications for multi-stakeholder discussions to facilitate evidence-based policy development. Ensuring that all research stakeholders are involved in the development of policy will foster a sense of ownership amongst the disparate communities, which will aid compliance.

Key objective: Facilitate the engagement of all research stakeholders in the development of institutional and national data policies to foster ownership and compliance

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
Historic lack of engagement between different communities	NRENs and non-governmental bodies can foster relationships between disparate communities
Need for expertise in mediation and mutual agenda-setting	Engage neutral parties to oversee agenda-setting activities

<p>Fragmented institutional, national and funding data sharing policies and differing priorities with respect to data sharing and openness</p>	<p>Any agenda-setting activities need to be preceded by workshops that clearly delineate agendas, priorities and perceptions of data sharing. Experiences from research networks such as H3Africa offer important lessons for agenda-setting and the protection of individual rights.</p>
<p>Need for multilateral skill transfer to ensure gainful agenda setting</p>	<p>Governments can offer internships to students interested in policy</p>

Table 8 Key challenges and solutions to facilitate the engagement of all research stakeholders in the development of institutional and national data policies to foster ownership and compliance

Integrate Data Skills Teaching in All Levels of Tertiary Academic Teaching

Open Data is both a set of values and a series of practical activities, and it is important that the training offered reflects both of these sides. The value-focused aspects of this training introduce students to the ethical underpinnings of the Open Science/Open Data movement, and engaging students in discussions about key topics such as collegiality, responsibility, justice and equity. Practical training, in contrast, involves providing students with the ability to utilize the many online tools available that facilitate open data sharing.

The concept of openness in research should be contextualized within broader training on responsible research practices, in particular RDM. Indeed, without the skills necessary for responsible data management and an understanding of the FAIR principles for data re-use, it is unlikely that any effective sharing and openness can be achieved. Identifying openness as a key component of responsible research practices makes a compelling case for how Open Data activities can enhance research quality.

Currently, levels of RDM training on the African continent are low, and improving provision of such training will undoubtedly involve the commitment of funds on institutional/national

and regional levels. Nonetheless, it is important to note the development of RDM curricula and training tools need not occur from scratch, and an extensive array of resources (detailed below) can assist in the roll-out of this training.

Over and above the importance that RDM plays to the establishment of Open Data cultures, committing to widespread training will have considerable benefits for the African research community. Current data management practices are extremely varied, and it is likely that a considerable amount of data produced through student projects, small grant activities and self-financed research ends up in flash-drives, unmarked folders or in spreadsheets without accompanying metadata. Training African researchers in RDM tools with a view towards Open Data will therefore enhance the quality and reproducibility of future research, and the likelihood of data being re-used.

Key objective: embed comprehensive Open Data training within tertiary education

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
Crowded curricula, lack of staff resources	Institutions must prioritize Open Data training and should commit funds towards rolling it out. Funders and national bodies should commit money towards supporting this training.
RDM training for researchers must be accompanied by training for ICT support staff, librarians and repository managers	Institutions must prioritize Open Data training and should commit funds towards rolling it out. Funders and national bodies should commit money towards supporting this training.
Staff unwilling to teach new material	Incentivise and support staff to include RDM, FAIR and Open Data topics in undergraduate curriculum and highlighting how these topics apply to <i>all</i> aspects of research cycle

Table 9 Key challenges and solutions for embedding comprehensive Open Data training within tertiary education

Engage the Public in Open Data Activities

According to a 2017 report by the European Commission, Open Science researchers have a range of different responsibilities, including:

- publishing under Open Access
- managing (open)data
- conducting professional research
- engaging with citizen science (o'Carroll, Kamerlin, *et al.*, 2017)

African research systems are making marked progress in the first three areas. In contrast, public engagement with science and citizen science activities remain low across the continent. As a result, there are few established systems of sharing research data with the general public or for ensuring that research data are accessible beyond academic communities.

Engaging the public in research is important for the longevity of Open Data cultures for a number of moral and practical reasons. In light of the former, Open Data strongly advocates for public access to data as a just return on public investment in research. Such access also underpins the egalitarian belief that data is a communal resource that does not belong to any specific sector of society. Improving public access to research data also has significant practical benefits, as it improves research transparency and public trust in research networks. Access to data also represents a resource that can be used by the public sector within the RDI sector. This may yield tangible benefits for the economy and for job creation (European Commission, 2015).

Key objective: engage the public in research through Open Data practices

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenge	Solution
Lack of historic traditions of public engagement with research	Draw on expertise from international citizen science communities to assist in roll-out of public engagement activities
Low science literacy within the general public	Partner with primary and secondary educational outreach programmes to foster science literacy from an early age
Lack of funds for public engagement	Institutions and governmental bodies should explicitly support engagement activities and citizen science communities

Table 10 Key challenges and solutions for engaging the public in research through Open Data practices

Develop National, Regional and Continent-Wide Cultures of Mutual Support

“Although science is an international enterprise, it is largely done within national and disciplinary systems that are organized, funded and motivated by national and disciplinary norms and practices. Effective open data in a data-intensive age can only be realised if there is systemic action at disciplinary, national and international levels. It is therefore imperative that national governments recognize the value to be gained from open data, for national science agencies to adopt a coordinating role, for science policy makers to set incentives for openness from universities and research institutions, for these institutions to support open data processes by their researchers and for learned societies that articulate the priorities and practices of their disciplines to advocate and facilitate open data processes as important priorities” (International Council for Science *et al.*, 2015, p. 6).

The timing of introducing Open Data practices to African research systems offers a unique opportunity to establish continent-wide coordination of data sharing practices. This stands in contrast to countries in the Global North, who have developed such practices piecemeal and often in isolation. African countries have the opportunity to learn from these various activities, adapt them for use in African research settings, and adopt them in a widespread coordinated effort. Initiatives such as the AOSP represent such a vision. Nonetheless, such a vision is only possible if, as discussed in the quote above, there are long term commitments from all research

stakeholders. Fostering this commitment requires not only the allocation of funds, it also the development of a shared vision and sustained support. Establishing this dispersed, and yet united community will ultimately determine the success of embedding Open Data in African research.

Activities to Address Specific Challenges Undermining Open Data Practices

Activities that encourage Open Data practices fall into 3 categories – those that encourage researchers to make data open, those that encourage the use of open data, and those that discourage closed data practices (International Council for Science *et al.*, 2015, p. 14). It is vital that these seemingly disparate activities are integrated to support an evolving landscape that supports the values underpinning openness. This section discusses some ways in which the challenges identified in the earlier section could be addressed and ameliorated in African settings. It is important to recognize that many of these actions can be applied at institutional, national and regional levels. The framework purposively does not make distinct categorisations, as the fundamental considerations are largely similar.

Developing ways to minimize barriers to Open Data practices offers a unique opportunity to scrutinize *how* research is conducted. Any system or framework that influences the way that research is done is based on – and perpetuates – sets of values. In this way, scrutinizing how research is governed, and questioning how practices could be more open affords us the opportunity to support key Open Science values, including equity, openness, collegiality,

quality and community (Long, 2016).⁷ African research is thus in a position to develop systems that support researchers' progress towards embodying important scholarly values (Konkiel, 2016).

Systems of Credit Attribution That Reflect Open Data Contributions

Frameworks of valuation and methods of incentivization not only inscribe, but reinforce a specific status quo of research practices. Thus, the values underpinning specific frameworks become entrenched within systems of research. Nowhere is this more prominent than the influence that publication-based metrics has had on the emergence of a culture of “publish or perish” within research.

As mentioned, the possible loss of credit for research outputs is regularly highlighted as a key reason why researchers are unwilling to share data (Ferguson, 2014; Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2016). It is recognized that publication-focused metrics are not adapted to measuring the re-use of data and physical resources. As these metrics are commonly used, both in Africa and globally, in assessing many aspects of academic research – from impact to promotion – they represent a significant barrier to the widespread adoption of Open Data practices.

While citation-based metrics can be used for data published in data journals, alternative data-level metrics are needed to measure attention and uptake of a dataset. These data-level metrics reflect real usage are currently being developed by a number of different parties,⁸ and are garnering considerable support. Similarly, there has been a rising interest in developing metrics that accurately reflect Open Science activities (see figure 6). These take into account a wide range of different activities, including open access to publications, open data, open peer review, research integrity, citizen science and stakeholder engagement. In such systems, researchers are rewarded when their responsible and open data practices contribute to the excellence of their research, and to other valued activities such as service and leadership, research impact and contribution to teaching.

⁷ This has been developed and adopted by novel metrics systems such as HuMetrics

⁸ Such as Fairmetrics and Make Data Count initiatives

Open Science Career Assessment Matrix (OS-CAM)	
<i>Open Science activities</i>	<i>Possible evaluation criteria</i>
RESEARCH OUTPUT	
Research activity	Pushing forward the boundaries of open science as a research topic
Publications	Publishing in open access journals Self-archiving in open access repositories
Datasets and research results	Using the FAIR data principles Adopting quality standards in open data management and open datasets Making use of open data from other researchers
Open source	Using open source software and other open tools Developing new software and tools that are open to other users
Funding	Securing funding for open science activities
RESEARCH PROCESS	
Stakeholder engagement / citizen science	Actively engaging society and research users in the research process Sharing provisional research results with stakeholders through open platforms (e.g. Arxiv, Figshare) Involving stakeholders in peer review processes
Collaboration and Interdisciplinarity	Widening participation in research through open collaborative projects Engaging in team science through diverse cross-disciplinary teams
Research integrity	Being aware of the ethical and legal issues relating to data sharing, confidentiality, attribution and environmental impact of open science activities Fully recognizing the contribution of others in research projects, including collaborators, co-authors, citizens, open data providers
Risk management	Taking account of the risks involved in open science
SERVICE AND LEADERSHIP	
Leadership	Developing a vision and strategy on how to integrate OS practices in the normal practice of doing research Driving policy and practice in open science Being a role model in practicing open science
Academic standing	Developing an international or national profile for open science activities Contributing as editor or advisor for open science journals or bodies
RESEARCH IMPACT	
Communication and Dissemination	Participating in public engagement activities Sharing research results through non-academic dissemination channels Translating research into a language suitable for public understanding
IP (patents, licenses)	Being knowledgeable on the legal and ethical issues relating to IPR Transferring IP to the wider economy
Societal impact	Evidence of use of research by societal groups Recognition from societal groups or for societal activities
Knowledge exchange	Engaging in open innovation with partners beyond academia
TEACHING AND SUPERVISION	
Teaching	Training other researchers in open science principles and methods Developing curricula and programs in open science methods, including open science data management Raising awareness and understanding in open science in undergraduate and masters' programs
Mentoring	Mentoring and encouraging others in developing their open science capabilities
Supervision	Supporting early stage researchers to adopt an open science approach
PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	
Continuing professional development	Investing in own professional development to build open science capabilities
Project management	Successfully delivering open science projects involving diverse research teams
Personal qualities	Demonstrating the personal qualities to engage society and research users with open science Showing the flexibility and perseverance to respond to the challenges of conducting open science

Figure 6: The Open Science assessment career matrix (o'Carroll, Rentier, *et al.*, 2017)

While such frameworks are urgently needed for evaluating African research, they should not be adopted wholesale from the Global North. Such metrics need to be adapted to better reflect not only the priorities but also the challenges of conducting research in Africa. In particular, it is important that metrics used to assess African research are able to make a distinction between

available and ideal pathways of dissemination. This will ensure that these Open Science/Open Data metrics do not impose yet another layer of unrealistic expectations on researchers who are working in unsupportive, resource-limited environments.

The development of such metrics will require considerable support from researchers, institutions, national governments, research networks and funders. Required activities include both the development of these metrics as well as rolling out training in their use. In terms of developing these metrics, key activities include:

- Reassessing existing evaluation-related criteria to ensure that they support data sharing activities.
- Engage in discussions as to how responsible data management, commitment to FAIR principles and open and effective data sharing can be operationalized as a primary indicator of research excellence
- Discuss how key aspects of Open Data, including openness, sharing, support to the community, implementation of FAIR principles, time investment, data and materials quality, impact, peer judgments, and usefulness to the field and to society can be evaluated
- Critically evaluate how variations in research contexts and infrastructural challenges can be factored in so as not to bias against some research communities

The development of research evaluation criteria that take into account Open Data/Open Science activities will need to be a collaborative effort involving all research stakeholders. Once such a set of metrics have been developed, the same stakeholders will need to commit to integrating it into their research-related practices. Key activities would include:

- *Researchers*: committing to appropriate crediting practices and teach these practices to students.
- *For research institutions*: include Open Science as a core means of assessing career impact, and use ORCID profiles in evaluation. Use CRediT-CASRAI badges⁹ in the researcher's activity assessment. Support researchers in the roll-out of Open Data activities.
- *For funders*: include FAIR sharing activity as a set of evaluation criteria, making it a strong requirement in all proposals.

⁹ <http://docs.casrai.org/CRediT>

- *For national governments:* Add sharing criteria to key performance indicators in institutional evaluations.
- *For all:* Avoid the exclusive use of quantitative assessment mechanisms such as impact factors in assessment processes.

Key objective: to develop metrics for research evaluation that take into account Open Data activities and are appropriate for use in evaluating African research

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
Researchers feeling overburdened by additional expectations	The adoption of such metrics must be accompanied by scrutiny of work practices and duties to enable researchers to accommodate the additional work required by Open Data activities
Constrained resources overburdened	Institutions, funders and governments must set aside money to fund Open Data activities if it is to become a method of research evaluation
Metrics supporting subset of researchers with resources and skills	Attention must be paid to the infrastructural burden of Open Data activities to ensure that researchers with the best infrastructures are not unfairly valued over others

Table 11 Key challenges and solutions to develop metrics for research evaluation that take into account Open Data activities

Shortage of Resources

It is well-recognized that sharing data requires resources. Financial resources, as well as time and expertise, are needed to establish physical and regulatory systems that support data sharing. They are also required resources to educate users to share data, use data-sharing infrastructures, as well as properly manage data and infrastructures for the common good.

It is important to note that many African institutions struggle with the impact of historical and current resource limitations, making it difficult for them to make large financial commitments to establishing Open Data practices amongst their staff. Nonetheless, as discussed above, key to establishing Open Data cultures and practices within institutions involves changing perceptions of data collections as *assets*, rather than unnecessary expenditure. This will play an important role in justifying the commitment of resources as a means of accruing reputational and collaborative benefits that will raise the institutional profile.

Committing scarce resources to Open Data activities must, however, also be done with caution. A lack of adequate Open Data training, poor planning of RDM and a lack of critical discussions about whether *all* data needs to be shared, it is possible that resources will be wasted that could be best applied elsewhere. It is therefore vital that Open Data activities be approached iteratively and pragmatically, ensuring that quality, FAIR data is shared effectively and appropriately. Initial outlays of resources will need to go into supporting this vision, including:

- Developing and rationalizing data sharing and IP policies
- Developing ethics policies/review frameworks for research data management that adequately scrutinize the possible implications of sharing data
- Allocating funds for dedicated technical support and training of technical support (IT, library, curatorial)
- Dedicate resources to RDM, FAIR and Open Data training for staff and students (self-archiving, standards for the identification, formatting and curation of data and metadata to make data reusable, publishing venue and related licensing, metrics and acknowledging and crediting the reuse)

Key objective: to elucidate how scarce resources can be most effectively spent when fostering Open Data practices

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenge	Solution
Waste of scarce resources due to poor planning and coordination	As Open Data is a multifaceted concept, training and resource investment can occur in multiple areas, funded by multiple

	organizations. Oversight is needed to ensure all initiatives align and are not tautologous.
Need for metrics that adequately demonstrate value of resource investment	How best to evaluate value of investment in Open Data practices is a topic of continuous discussion. African institutions need to develop explicit metrics so as to avoid funding “fatigue” due to lack of evidence of changes in cultures and practices
Situations in which the “urgent drives out the important”	Investing in culture development can easily fall by the wayside in the face of critical resource shortages. A firm commitment to Open Data by all research stakeholders is needed to ensure that Open Data remains on funding agendas

Table 12 Key challenges and solutions for elucidating how scarce resources can be most effectively spent when fostering Open Data practices

Diversity of Practices and Policies

Data management is a relatively new topic within African research, and many institutions, funders and national governments have yet to develop comprehensive regulatory frameworks to govern research data. Moreover, national and international funders often have different requirements for data management and sharing. This can leave African researchers in difficult positions, as they are subject to incomplete, unclear or conflicting data requirements. This can leave them unwilling to engage in Open Data activities for fear of defaulting on regulatory requirements.

In order to support data sharing, and to safeguard equitable practices, it is vital that African institutions, funders and national bodies be encouraged to collaborate on developing frameworks that clearly identify common principles and expectations. Such frameworks should include statements on:

- *Data availability and accessibility*: commits users to release data with as few restrictions as possible in a timely and responsible manner
- *Data management*: identifies relevant standards and community best practice
- *Data re-use and discoverability*: highlights expectations surrounding metadata etc
- *Legal, ethical and commercial issues*: takes into consideration, explains and endorses any constraints on release of research data
- *Data citation*: commits users to properly crediting intellectual contributors, data sources, terms etc
- *Efficiency and cost-effectiveness*: highlights the importance of maximising the research benefit which can be gained from budgets, the mechanisms for the research activities should be efficient and cost-effective in the use of public funds. (this list is adapted from Kvalheim and Kvamme, 2014, p. 8).

Achieving frameworks that reflect the position of multiple research stakeholders will not only be of considerable importance for clarifying the responsibilities of researchers. Endorsing and using such frameworks will further foster a culture of African Open Science, as it commits stakeholders to a specific level of behaviour, as well as to the principles underpinning them. Thus, frameworks need to be explicit about how the different areas of actions contribute to upholding Open Data values such as openness, collegiality, quality and community (Long, 2016). They must also support associated RDM values, such as flexibility, transparency, legal conformity and accountability, together with the FAIR principles of interoperability and reproducibility.

Such frameworks are a commitment to professionalism in data production and dissemination, and therefore must be considered to be associated with formal (or role) responsibilities for all stakeholders. There are a wide range of resources that can assist institutions in developing data policies and data access arrangements. These include those focusing on the use of research data, such as the OECD *Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding*,¹⁰ or the EPSRC *Principles Informing Decisions on Research Data Management*.

The AOSP will play an important role in the development of a landscape of frameworks and regulations. It is in a good position to serve as a central body to collate and coordinate data

¹⁰ <http://www.oecd.org/sti/sci-tech/38500813.pdf>

sharing policies, and to foster networks of support, advice and good practice. It will also be in a position to act as a conduit between these African frameworks and the international regulatory landscape.

Institutions, funders, publishers and governments are in the position to decide on the manner in which commitments to openness are to be rolled out within research communities. Approaches could vary considerably, from more “hands off” approaches to those that mandate consequences for non-compliance (such as being temporarily ineligible for further funding). Variability within these approaches is not necessarily a bad thing, and depends on the context and available funds.

Key objective: to strengthen and rationalize the regulatory landscape governing Open Data practices

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenges	Solutions
The development of policies must be representative of all research contexts, and not just the most visible data producers at centers of excellence or the best-funded institutions.	There is considerable variability within African research institutions with regards to funding and availability of resources. Any development of frameworks and strategies must include representatives from all institutions within a national landscape.
Mandating data sharing before the necessary infrastructure in place will invariably lead to disillusionment and researcher fatigue.	Rolling out any Open Data initiative should be timed to accompany infrastructure investments. Any initiative, policy or metric be properly piloted in a number of different settings to make sure it is supportable by the existing infrastructures.

Table 13 Key challenges and solutions for strengthening and rationalizing the regulatory landscape governing Open Data practice

Intellectual Property

The intellectual property (IP) landscape in Africa is complicated and in many cases existing legislation does not adequately cover research outputs – particularly data. Despite African countries placing R&D at the centre of their developmental agendas (African Union, 2014; African Union Commission, 2015), research stakeholders are often confused as to how best to protect their research outputs. This situation is complicated by a paucity of dedicated IP advice departments at African institutions that are able to offer insights into how the intricacies of data, openness and IP.

The concerns surrounding loss of IP are compounded by a number of factors discussed elsewhere in this document. First, many researchers in Africa are highly concerned about being “scooped”. This concern, coupled with lack of clarity on IP issues, often stops any Open Data activities. Second, many researchers in African utilize their personal funds to undertake research projects, and are therefore expecting a return on their investment. This can make them unwilling to share data without a guarantee of some form of protection (Louise Bezuidenhout, Kelly, *et al.*, 2017). Third, many research institutions are starting to aggressively pursue IP as a potential source of income. This does not necessarily mean, however, that all IP pursued is commercializable, meaning that restrictive institutional IP regulations can curtail the sharing of useful, but commercially worthless, information.

There is an urgent need to support the development of comprehensive IP legislation that also supports open research. This will require not only engagement with research stakeholders, but with the growing community of scholars and practitioners that are developing Open IP and open licenses. NRENs and national academies could play an important role in coordinating these activities, as they possess the objectivity and influence to navigate this landscape.

Key objective: to develop the African IP landscape to support FAIR/Open Data practices

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenge	Solution
Widespread lack of clarity about IP and Open Data	Ensure that African research networks are engaged in evolving global discussions on IP and Open Data

Complicated national legislative landscapes and pieces of conflicting legislation and regulation	Facilitate national review of legal landscapes and the identification of areas pertaining to data sharing that require attention. Such activities could be facilitated by NRENs, national academies or governmental bodies
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Table 14 Key challenges and solutions of developing African IP landscape to support FAIR/Open Data practices

Authorship and Data Curation

Publishers have many responsibilities within the Open Data paradigm, including setting standards for openness and citation within the papers they publish. Journals and repositories based on the African continent will thus play an important role in the evolution of the data sharing landscape. In particular, they will play two important roles. First, African journals and repositories will establish standards for Open/FAIR data that are aligned with the Open Data career metrics discussed above. Second, together with libraries, NRENs and national academies, they will serve as points for advice for African researchers wishing to engage with the broader Open Data landscape.

There are a number of different activities that can assist them in achieving these goals. Perhaps most important is to establish practices that ensure that African research outputs are assigned persistent identifiers¹¹ connected to the digital academic sphere. African journals also need to develop comprehensive instructions for authors that will help them to choose a proper repository for archiving data. More broadly, however, African journals need to scrutinize their commitments to the Open Science movement and consider how they can foster openness. This will include ensuring that their requirements for authorship accreditation adequately reflect all contributors to research outputs.

As is discussed in related AOSP frameworks, establishing a network of trusted African repositories is key to the expansion of Open Data on the continent. It is thus of importance that libraries, NRENs and national academies collate lists of repositories that comply with Trusted

¹¹ Such as Digital Object Identifier, DOI from Datacite (www.datacite.org)

Digital Repository criteria that warrant open, trustworthy and long-term preservation. A number of different initiatives have scrutinized online repositories and have developed tools to guide researchers in their selections. These include checklists for evaluating repositories,¹² and online lists such as those collated by FAIRsharing (fairsharing.org) and Re3data (re3data.org). Journals, libraries, NRENs and national academies should also work with repositories struggling to comply with these criteria to foster good practice, instead of penalizing bad.

Key objective: to enhance openness in African journals and repositories

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenge	Solution
Publishers and repositories do not recognize need to change current formats	Funders and governmental bodies can adopt a stronger position on Open Science, similar to Plan S in the EU
Lack of coordination between publishers and repositories leads to multiple contrasting Open Science policies	Workshops can be held to establish contact between editors and curators, and to form a network for mutual collaboration and policy development

Table 15 Key challenges and solutions for enhancing openness in African journals and repositories

Ethical Issues

Within Open Data discussions it is generally agreed that data should be released into the public domain as soon as possible after creation. Nonetheless, it is also important to recognize that how this is done responsibly varies according to the types of data being shared, and the context in which it was created. It is well-recognized that some data cannot – and should not – be shared due to ethical concerns about privacy, consent, security, or the possible causing of harm. Recognizing that responsible data sharing involves considering such ethical concerns is fundamental to responsible Open Data practices.

¹² http://www.crl.edu/sites/default/files/d6/attachments/pages/trac_0.pdf

There are a number of well-established research networks operating in Africa that have developed detailed data sharing/Open Data policies that meet the specific ethical requirements of their datasets. In particular, those operating in the medical/clinical research field, together with research in emergency/disaster situations (such as the recent Ebola outbreak) have given rise to very comprehensive data sharing policies that could be of use to the African research community more broadly. It will be of considerable use if these communities are approached for their data sharing policies, so that national or institutional bodies can critically examine them for lessons learnt.

Key objective: develop robust ethical policies to safeguard responsible Open Data practices

Key challenges and solutions:

Challenge	Solution
Evaluating data sharing policies from an ethical perspective is a skill. In particular, as the range of data being submitted for review (including artificial intelligence research, algorithms and so forth) becomes more varied, many African institutional Research Ethics Committees (RECs) may feel unprepared to conduct in-depth reviews.	National and international bodies support RECs to receive additional training on Open Data and data sharing. ¹³

Table 16 Key challenges and solution for developing robust ethical policies to safeguard responsible Open Data practices

Infrastructure, Hardware and Software

Effective data practices require hardware, software and ICT infrastructures. The absence of effective and integrated ICT systems plays a critical role in determining whether Open Data practices are taken up or rejected. These infrastructural challenges are addressed in related AOSP frameworks, and will not be covered here in detail.

¹³ Such a project could gain from lessons learnt by a current IDRC/NRF project that is working with African grant funding councils to strengthen capacity in order to support research and evidence-based policies <https://sgciafrica.org/en-za>

Anticipated Outputs

The section above gave a long list of different actions that will contribute towards the adoption of Open Data practices within the African research community. Some of these actions are immediately implementable, and some will require longer-term investments in time and resources. Committing to these different actions will have some important outputs that can be measured. In relation to resources, such outputs would include an increase the funds dedicated to Open Data activities, and an improved roll-out of RDM/FAIR/Open Data training within African research.

In terms of community development, it will be possible to measure increased support for Open Data through the increased citation of African data DOIs, and the increased deposition of data in institutional, national and international repositories. It will also potentially be possible to chart the increased use of altmetric sharing pathways by African researchers by assessing their activity on key platforms such as FigShare. The AOSP will play an important role in developing tools to track the activities of African researchers – both as users and sharers of data.

This framework understands Open Data activities as also including teaching and mentoring activities. Measurable outcomes in these areas will include the development and sharing of Open Data/RDM/FAIR open educational resources, and the establishment and support for Open Data champion networks and examples of good practice. If the concerns about current publication-focused metrics of valuation and credit are taken on board, it will also be possible to chart the development of these metrics for use in African institutions. Indeed, the AOSP could play an important centralized coordination function in these evolving discussions.

Necessary areas for Open Data cultures	Areas of action	Challenges	Activities suggested	Metrics

People	Mindset	Lack of awareness of Open Data	<p>Awareness raising activities amongst all research stakeholders</p> <p>Encourage development of formal and informal cultures of Open Data</p> <p>Increase African representation in global Open Data community</p> <p>Curate positive examples of Open Data champions</p>	<p>Increase in membership of African researchers to international organizations promoting Open Data, such as RDA</p> <p>Increase in representation of African researchers at Open Data conferences, such as International Data Week</p> <p>Scientometrics evidence of changing African researcher and authorship, data re-use practices</p> <p>Increase in the deposition of African data in internationally trusted repositories</p>
	Incentives	Authorship Evaluation and credit	<p>Develop Open Science career evaluation metrics</p> <p>Improve authorship criteria in African journals</p>	<p>Institutions and funding bodies committing to re-evaluating their existing metrics for assessing research impact</p> <p>The growth of an African discussion about evaluation</p>

				metrics, potentially focused on how best to adapt the Open Science career assessment metrics
	Skills	Lack of data science/RDM skills	Roll-out RDM training for researchers and technical support staff	Demonstrable increase in Open Data-related teaching at institutional, national and regional levels Measurable rise in the development and open sharing of Open Data educational material developed for use in African contexts
Processes and organisations	Support	Low institutional support Lack of technical support	Improve awareness of datasets as an asset Improve training for librarians and technical staff	Institutional and national funding for Open Data training The development of institutional and national repositories Investment in data science training Support for curation and technical support Provision for data sharing activities in time allocations of staff

	Funding	Lack of funding for Open Data initiatives	Encourage institutions, funders and governments to explicitly support Open Data activities	Measurable increase in funding for Open Data activities
	Ecosystem	Confusing legal/IP landscape Complicated ethical issues Lack of engagement between research stakeholders	Support the critical scrutiny of national and institutional governance landscapes to improve support and protection for Open Data activities	Improved registration of African repositories according to Re3data Increased number of national and regional Open Data meetings between stakeholders, disciplines, national research systems
Technology	Consent	Complicated ethical issues around ownership, privacy and informed consent		
	Technical	ICT infrastructures, hardware and software		

Figure 7: Areas of activity necessary for establishing Open Data cultures (International Council for Science *et al.*, 2015, p. 11) associated with challenges, activities and potential metrics

A Rise in Measurable Open Data Events Within African Academia

If Open Data is correctly incentivized amongst African research stakeholders it is feasible to assume that there will be a rise in Open Data-related activities within African academia. Such activities could be monitored multiple areas, including:

- the membership of African researchers to international organizations promoting Open Data, such as RDA
- the representation of African researchers at Open Data conferences, such as International Data Week
- the increase in Open Data-related teaching at institutional, national and regional levels

As mentioned above, however, African research institutions vary considerably in terms of historic legacy, resource provision, and regulatory/bureaucratic structures. Their ability to conduct research is also influenced by national infrastructures, and governmental, private-sector and public support. All of these factors influence the establishment and adoption of Open Data cultures, as well as shaping the types of data sharing practices that institutions and researchers engage with. Recognizing this variability is extremely important for any framework to incentivize data sharing, and highlights the importance of avoiding “one size fits all” mindsets.

Closer scrutiny of this variability also draws attention to some often-overlooked issues that need to be addressed during the roll-out of this framework. First, efforts to assess the efficacy of this framework and other AOSP activities should not rely on feedback from the “most visible” communities. While it is understandable that well-resourced, or historically more-engaged institutions will have more visible Open Data cultures, this should not detract from assessing the activities in institutions with smaller or newer programmes. Similarly, scrutiny of data sharing practices should not rely solely on the “low hanging fruit” of established international research networks.

A related caution is that assessments of the development of Open Data cultures should not aim to identify “best practice”, but rather an “acceptable minimum” that institutions can improve on. While “best practice” discourse does serve as being aspirational, it can also alienate and discourage individuals/institutions who do not have the resources or support to implement these desired activities.

Changing Means of Evaluating Research in Africa

An important driver for establishing Open Data practices within African academia will be by changing the availability of incentives. In particular, changing the way in which research and researchers are evaluated will play a key role in the roll-out of data sharing practices on a continent-wide level. These changing formats for evaluation will be measurable by:

- Institutions and funding bodies committing to re-evaluating their existing metrics for assessing research impact
- The growth of an African discussion about evaluation metrics, potentially focused on how best to adapt the Open Science career assessment metrics

It is important, however, to recognize that any scheme of incentivization – no matter how well-intentioned – can be the cause of future negative behaviour if improperly designed, applied or scrutinized. It is possible that efforts to promote data sharing amongst African researchers could be undermined if the application of incentives leads to “gaming” amongst the researchers, leading to data dumping or excessive publication as a means of playing the system.

It is therefore of particular importance that considerable effort be put into developing series of metrics that are an appropriate reflection not only of data sharing in Africa, but also reflect the long-term values of the Open Data movement. Assessing the development of these metrics for use in African academia is therefore not sufficient in its own right, but should be accompanied by long-term evaluations to safeguard against possible unintended negative outcomes.

Increase in Resources Dedicated to Open Data Activities

One of the most pragmatic indicators of a rise in Open Data support is, of course, whether stakeholders are willing to commit resources to data sharing activities. Such resources include financial contributions, but also time and expertise. Measuring an increase in resources dedicated to Open Data activities could be done assessing a rise in:

- institutional and national funding for Open Data training
- the development of institutional and national repositories

- investment in data science training
- support for curation and technical support
- provision for data sharing activities in time allocations of staff
- funding for Open Data activities

It is important to again reiterate how the variability of African research institutions could potentially skew any assessment activities, as some researchers/institutions/nations will have more resources at their disposal to contribute to Open Data activities. It is important that these variations be taken into account when assessing the roll-out of Open Data activities.

Increased Visibility of African Research Online and Re-Use of African Research Outputs

Engaging in Open Data practices such as the assignment of DOIs to datasets and papers, improved citation and crediting practices, and enhanced transparency, facilitate efforts to improve the re-use of African research online. Moreover, the use of altmetric sharing platforms to disseminate data further increases the spread of African research data online. Together, these contribute to the enhanced visibility and re-usability of African data online. This can be monitored by:

- using scientometrics to track authorship, data re-use and other indicators of visibility, collaboration and re-use
- monitoring the registration of African repositories using Re3data or other applicable means

African research has previously been criticized for being siloed, with low levels of South-South cooperation between institutions. New funding models, as well as endorsement from the AOSP, will undoubtedly encourage further in-continent collaboration. Nonetheless, these traditions of isolation are not necessarily overcome overnight, and may be underpinned by significant socio-cultural issues, such as competition for finite national resources encouraging rivalry. Further investigation into these barriers is necessary to ensure that these issues are effectively overcome.

Due to low levels of national and international research funding, many researchers continue to self-fund their research using their own private finances. This has been noted as problematic

for Open Data discussions, as it changes attitudes of ownership, reward and compensation (Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2016; L. Bezuidenhout *et al.*, 2017). Many scientists will remain unwilling to share privately-funded data, regardless of emerging data infrastructures. Changing this unwillingness will require not only cultural changes and sustained engagement, but also changes to current funding structures.

Anticipated Effects

The comprehensive implementation of the recommendations within this framework will yield a number of short- and long-term results.

Growth of the Active African Open Data Community

If data sharing is properly incentivized it will lead to the development of communities of research that are recognizable by commonly-held values and standards of practice. Thus, while these communities of practice can vary considerably according to discipline or subdomain, they continue to be united by commonly-held values. It is important that African researchers develop communities of practice that are tailored to the needs and challenges of their research disciplines and settings, yet united by commitments to openness, equity and quality.

The Open Data landscape is expanding at a considerable rate, and influences everything from funding requirements to evaluations of responsible research. It is increasingly important that African voices are included in the development of this landscape, to ensure that the priorities and challenges experienced by African researchers are included into the design of future infrastructures.

As the African Open Data landscape evolves, it will also become important to include other key data producers in discussions. These will include national governments, NGOs and commercial companies. Outreach and discussion will be important to ensure that evolving Open Data structures within research are flexible and adaptable enough to gradually incorporate data produced by these stakeholders.

Changing the Way African Science is Practiced

Implementing Open Data practices within African research will have significant implications for the practice of science on the continent. If, as suggested by this framework, the values of Open Data are used to orient policy and practice changes, it can readily be assumed will lead to a more responsible, open, equitable and transparent academic culture. This will ensure robust research communities capable of sustaining research capacity building activities.

Changing metrics of evaluation and promotion from publication-focused to those reflecting the multifarious activities inherent in Open Science will also have significant benefits for academic institutions, African publishers and national research systems. Broadening evaluation metrics can be anticipated to decrease competitive behaviour between researchers and lead to enhanced collaboration and cooperation. It will also ensure that emphasis is placed on the production of high-quality publications, and not the “minimum publishable unit”, a problem which causes much research to be dissipated in small journal articles and low-quality journals. Similarly, the implementation of such metrics will strengthen research systems, by bringing to the fore research that has true global impact.

Making data sharing the default position for African science will also be beneficial for enhancing its reproducibility and transparency. While the quality and quantity of data production in African research is increasing steadily, the region remains an emerging area of scientific excellence. Making sure that African data can be properly scrutinized, will ensure that quality research is recognized by the international research community.

Development of Robust Open Data Infrastructures

Incentivizing institutions and national governments to support Open Data activities has implications for RDM more broadly. As discussed in this, and related AOSP frameworks, a commitment to Open Data requires investment in ICT technologies and infrastructures on all levels. Such investments range from the increased provision of up-to-date ICT hardware and

software to researchers, to strengthened library systems and institutional repositories, to national broadband infrastructures.

Widespread investment in ICT technologies and infrastructures will have significant results for accelerating research capacity in Africa. Multifaceted investment into connectivity will enhance research practices and speed up data outputs. Moreover, encouraging researchers to engage in multifarious data sharing practices will enhance the visibility of African academia internationally.

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